

WorldFAIR WP13 CULTURAL HERITAGE FIP01

Organization	GO FAIR
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Based on	FIP Wizard 3, 0.0.3 (gofair:fip-wizard-3:0.0.3)
Project Phase	never
Project Tags	CODATA Type: FIP WorldFAIR
Created at	15 May 2023

I. About

Questions

No questions

II. Declare your FAIR Implementation Community

Questions

1

Select your FAIR Implementation Community

WorldFAIR WP13 CULTURAL HERITAGE

Community for WP13 Cultural Heritage in the WorldFAIR Project, investigating the image sharing practices of cultural heritage institutions and services with the goal of making recommendations for improving and aligning existing image sharing platforms and standards, and developing a framework for FAIR assessment and benchmarking in cultural heritage.

http://purl.org/np/RAyqHC4Dc5OFKtYmoZ6L_bhLoFupBEZyoTkN6jaxDIXC4#wf-wp13-cultural-heritage

2

Who is the Community Data Steward?

0000-0003-3108-3921

3

Specify the start date for the validity of the FIP

2022-09-19

4

Specify the end date for the validity of the FIP

2024-05-31

III. Declarations for Findability

Questions

1

Declaration F1 Metadata: What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

DOI | Digital Object Identifier

The digital object identifier (DOI) system originated in a joint initiative of three trade associations in the publishing industry (International Publishers Association; International Association of Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers; Association of American Publishers). The system was announced at the Frankfurt Book Fair 1997. The International DOI Foundation (IDF) was created to develop and manage the DOI system, also in 1997. The DOI system was adopted as International Standard ISO 26324 in 2012. The DOI system implements the Handle System and adds a number of new features. The DOI system provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type. The DOI system is designed to work over the Internet. A DOI name is permanently assigned to an object to provide a resolvable persistent network link to current information about that object, including where the object, or information about it, can be found on the Internet. While information about an object can change over time, its DOI name will not change. A DOI name can be resolved within the DOI system to values of one or more types of data relating to the object identified by that DOI name, such as a URL, an e-mail address, other identifiers and descriptive metadata. The DOI system enables the construction of automated services and transactions. Applications of the DOI system include but are not limited to managing information and documentation location and access; managing metadata; facilitating electronic transactions; persistent unique identification of any form of any data; and commercial and non-commercial transactions. The content of an object associated with a DOI name is described unambiguously by DOI metadata, based on a structured extensible data model that enables the object to be associated with metadata of any desired degree of precision and granularity to support description and services. The data model supports interoperability between DOI applications. The scope of the DOI system is not defined by reference to the type of content (format, etc.) of the referent, but by reference to

the functionalities it provides and the context of use. The DOI system provides, within networks of DOI applications, for unique identification, persistence, resolution, metadata and semantic interoperability.

http://purl.org/np/RAnAWGdel_1GGmDAqv-vZjby5XqbL2ZujNz1vgwK_6cRI#DOI

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- This question has not been answered yet!*

1.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

**** Open Researcher and Contributor ID****

ORCID provides a persistent digital identifier (an ORCID iD) that you own and control, and that distinguishes you from every other researcher. You can connect your iD with your professional information — affiliations, grants, publications, peer review, and more. You can use your iD to share your information with other systems, ensuring you get recognition for all your contributions, saving you time and hassle, and reducing the risk of errors.

http://purl.org/np/RAch6DyoYVD3iuaALPR32ZPAZTvbw_ulid9E7Dnc67GtA#ORCID

1.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration

- ✓ ORCIDs are often provided by the depositor 'in' the metadata as a link that resolves to a researcher's ORCID page. Some repositories or publishers also push metadata to a researcher's ORCID page.

2

Declaration F1 Data: What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for datasets?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DOI | Digital Object Identifier

The digital object identifier (DOI) system originated in a joint initiative of three trade associations in the publishing industry (International Publishers Association; International Association of Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers; Association of American Publishers). The system was announced at the Frankfurt Book Fair 1997. The International DOI Foundation (IDF) was created to develop and manage the DOI system, also in 1997. The DOI system was adopted as International Standard ISO 26324 in 2012. The DOI system implements the Handle System and adds a number of new features. The DOI system provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type. The DOI system is designed to work over the Internet. A DOI name is permanently assigned to an object to provide a resolvable persistent network link to current information about that object, including where the object, or information about it, can be found on the Internet. While information about an object can change over time, its DOI name will not change. A DOI name can be resolved within the DOI system to values of one or more types of data relating to the object identified by that DOI name, such as a URL, an e-mail address, other identifiers and descriptive metadata. The DOI system enables the construction of

automated services and transactions. Applications of the DOI system include but are not limited to managing information and documentation location and access; managing metadata; facilitating electronic transactions; persistent unique identification of any form of any data; and commercial and non-commercial transactions. The content of an object associated with a DOI name is described unambiguously by DOI metadata, based on a structured extensible data model that enables the object to be associated with metadata of any desired degree of precision and granularity to support description and services. The data model supports interoperability between DOI applications. The scope of the DOI system is not defined by reference to the type of content (format, etc.) of the referent, but by reference to the functionalities it provides and the context of use. The DOI system provides, within networks of DOI applications, for unique identification, persistence, resolution, metadata and semantic interoperability.

http://purl.org/np/RAnAWGdel_1GGmDAqv-vZjby5XqbL2ZujNz1vgwK_6cRI#DOI

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- X** This question has not been answered yet!

3

Declaration F2: What metadata schema do you use for findability?

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DataCite Metadata Scheme

The DataCite Metadata Schema is a list of core metadata properties chosen for an accurate and consistent identification of a resource for citation and retrieval

http://purl.org/np/RAko0U2Q8boW-drM8t11DcbX6lXu2mcSQf-2BrM07geIQ#datacite_metadata_scheme

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

This question has not been answered yet!

3.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DC | Dublin Core

The Dublin Metadata Element Set, which is often called Dublin Core (DC), is a standardized metadata scheme for description of any kind of resource such as documents in electronic and non-electronic form, digital materials (such as video, sound, images, etc) and composite media like web pages. Dublin Core Metadata may be used for multiple purposes, from simple resource description, to combining metadata vocabularies of different metadata standards, to providing interoperability for metadata vocabularies in the Linked Data cloud and Semantic Web implementations. Please note that this version of the specification for the Dublin Core Element Set 1.1 is somewhat out of date, although it is not officially

deprecated. The DCMI Metadata Terms specification is linked to this record and is the current documentation that should be used for the Dublin Core Element Set 1.1.

http://purl.org/np/RApwFvegOdPfNuKIF64wctAzaffAv3j_2kAU9y6kfBoy8#DCMI

3.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration

- Both simple and qualified Dublin Core are used.

3.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Europeana Data Model for Cultural Heritage (EDM)

The Europeana Data Model (EDM) aims to bridge the gaps between metadata standards used by a wide range of data providers from the library, museum, archive, and audio-visual sectors in order for the data to appear in a meaningful way in a cross-cultural, multilingual context such as Europeana. EDM is a data model that links Europe's cultural heritage data.

<http://purl.org/np/RAIccZ6j-6IF7tY8Yqdk9gDBWPW44pTVKh9D-AF-Lt-1g#europeana-dm>

3.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration

- ✓ Only used for the purposes of publishing to Europeana.

4

Declaration F3: What is the schema that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

4.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

5

Declaration F4 Metadata: Which service do you use to publish your metadata records?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

5.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

5.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Europeana

Europeana is a meta-aggregator for European cultural heritage from institutions across Europe.

<http://purl.org/np/RAY9qwRnRwMcXjLCH3-cicAeeseoCQbMV3kIVyQ6zVZEw#europeana>

5.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- This question has not been answered yet!*

6

Declaration F4 Datasets: Which service do you use to publish your datasets?

- This question has not been answered yet!*

IV. Declarations for Accessibility

Questions

1

Declaration A1.1 Metadata: Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2

Declaration A1.1 Datasets: Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3

Declaration A1.2 Metadata: Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for metadata records?

✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

4

Declaration A1.2 Datasets: Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for datasets?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

4.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

4.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

OAuth | Open Authorization

OAuth 2.0 is the industry-standard protocol for authorization. OAuth 2.0 focuses on client developer simplicity while providing specific authorization flows for web applications, desktop applications, mobile phones, and living room devices.

<http://purl.org/np/RAbhCIJzwMFVkgwvrhsdjnpxtH58oLKoyxgj60DzkS-q4#OAuth>

4.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

This question has not been answered yet!

4.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Edugate

Edugate is HEAnet's federated single sign-on (SSO) service which authenticates across Ireland's

National Education & Research Network.

<http://purl.org/np/RAvEMOFdBCvYiYAYW1CM8wW7rLCMU4QOOHUsQiUKqz2Wg#edugate-HEAnet>

4.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration

- The DRI allows the depositor to set access restrictions on their data. Data can be available publicly, to logged-in users only, or restricted to named individuals (see the Restricted Data Policy). DRI also enables restriction of access to those with Edugate usernames and passwords. These access restrictions are implemented via a custom user and groups code library developed by DRI which stores the permissions as technical metadata alongside each object or collection (this technical metadata can be accessed only by the developer team). Users may request access to data via the web interface.

5

Declaration A2: What metadata preservation policy do you use?

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

5.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

5.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

RDA CTS | RDA Core Trust Seal Certification

The RDA Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership Working Group (WG) produced a two-part recommendation, one of which includes a Catalogue of Common Procedures for certification. The goal of the effort was to create a set of harmonized Common Procedures for certification of repositories at the basic level, drawing from the procedures already put in place by the Data Seal of Approval (DSA) and the ICSU World Data System (ICSU–WDS). These procedures are intended to support the implementation of the Catalogue of Common Requirements developed by the WG to harmonize the certification criteria previously established by the DSA and ICSU-WDS.

http://purl.org/np/RA6JGt5TRNo9XpCM5XcNKIhEDIGWTvZ6iUyhff0bfwX4#RDA_CTS

5.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

This question has not been answered yet!

V. Declarations for Interoperability

Questions

1

Declaration I1 Metadata: What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

JSON-LD | JavaScript Object Notation for Linking Data

JSON-LD is a JSON-based format to serialize Linked Data. The syntax is designed to easily integrate into deployed systems that already use JSON, and provides a smooth upgrade path from JSON to JSON-LD. It is primarily intended to be a way to use Linked Data in Web-based programming environments, to build interoperable Web services, and to store Linked Data in JSON-based storage engines. JSON-LD is a concrete RDF syntax. A JSON-LD document is both an RDF document and a JSON document and correspondingly represents an instance of an RDF data model. However, JSON-LD also extends the RDF data model to optionally allow JSON-LD to serialize generalized RDF Datasets.

http://purl.org/np/RAQKjgd7Ug9xSo4J0REW_AHGOJyaF9-ydj60nungQ0qVg#JSON-LD

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

1.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

RDF | Resource Description Framework

The Resource Description Framework (RDF) is a framework for representing information in the Web.

<http://purl.org/np/RAutRQwoS4d5eLq7eBV1xsnWZ2spDYH4xfhhRzOxSZdhs#RDF>

1.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

1.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

XMLS | eXtensible Markup Language Schema

XMLS defines and describes a class of XML documents by using schema components to constrain and

document the meaning, usage and relationships of their constituent parts: datatypes, elements and their content and attributes and their values.

http://purl.org/np/RA5E0NA_BAilxwHhZKQm-ltnF0xw3atel8UFxZ0rs8N5Q#XML_Schema

1.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration

- This question has not been answered yet!*

2

Declaration I1 Datasets: What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF)

IIIF is a set of open standards for delivering high-quality, attributed digital objects online at scale. It's

also an international community developing and implementing the IIIF APIs. IIIF is backed by a consortium of leading cultural institutions.

<http://purl.org/np/RAiPPu60BXJzqREvhZ1bchfK9W2HvmD3NaNhH1NHC8J0A#IIIF>

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Tag Image File Format (TIFF)

A TIFF is a computer file used to store raster graphics and image information. The file might have either a .tiff or .tif extension.

<http://purl.org/np/RAi2XqkUsg08QLQ6HuS7PXHREjruRsfCTpr7oFSMR3dPI#tiff>

2.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

JPEG File Format

JPEG is a commonly used method of lossy compression for digital images, particularly for those images produced by digital photography. The file might have a .jpg or .jpeg extension.

http://purl.org/np/RAqJhu6LHwidmg3dB7vGx6JIEM_3U2g6sKntmGasoccak#jpeg

2.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.d.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Portable Network Graphics (PNG)

PNG is a raster-graphics file format that supports lossless data compression. PNG files use the file

extension .png and have been assigned the MIME media type image/png.

http://purl.org/np/RAeQ9BaFx_qAuhqOmsg4EG0QjIV8fsr4X0cL2SYLZsxo#png

2.b.1.d.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.d.3

Implementation Consideration

This question has not been answered yet!

2.b.1.e.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Portable Document Format (PDF)

*The Portable Document Format (PDF), standardized as ISO 32000, is a file format developed by Adobe in 1992 to present documents, including text formatting and images, in a manner independent of application software, hardware, and operating systems. Based on the PostScript language, each PDF file encapsulates a complete description of a fixed-layout flat document, including the text, fonts, vector graphics, raster images and other information needed to display it. *

http://purl.org/np/RAuxR5Gx_uvVbVoePV226Lk86VRYrh9EpmqFXU7f_ojQ#pdf

2.b.1.e.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.e.3

Implementation Consideration

- ✓ This format is not commonly used for image content only, but text files with images embedded may be rendered as PDF.

2.b.1.f.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

STL File Format

STL is a file format native to the stereolithography CAD software created by 3D Systems. STL files describe only the surface geometry of a three-dimensional object without any representation of colour, texture or other common CAD model attributes. The files are commonly used for 3D printing.

<http://purl.org/np/RANdu24xclIQrF1TLXJ-mlwcMzEh07pM5HCJN3sXv2ieY#stl>

2.b.1.f.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.f.3

Implementation Consideration

- ✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.g.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

E57 Lidar Point Cloud Data Format

A file with .e57 extension is a compact, vendor-neutral file format that is used for storing and exchange of three-dimensional (3D) imaging data such as point clouds, images, and metadata. E57 is open source and stores 3D point data, its attributes (such as colour and intensity), and 2D imagery as captured by the 3D imaging system.

http://purl.org/np/RASXVtpeoMwtc-zoPDGe0N1qau_z-e5-kmNc1AW4K42uY#e57

2.b.1.g.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.g.3

Implementation Consideration

- This question has not been answered yet!*

3

Declaration I2 Metadata: What structured vocabulary do you use to annotate your metadata records?

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DCMI Metadata Terms|Dublin Core Metadata Terms

DCMI is the vocabulary for the Dublin Core metadata schemes.

http://purl.org/np/RAtBs7WUCXYRMmdDGKDEwYlyjJCC3bc0KWXTjlfJHiW_E#DCMI_terms

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- This question has not been answered yet!*

3.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH)

*Library of Congress Subject Headings has been actively maintained since 1898 to catalog materials held at the Library of Congress. Many other libraries in the United States, Canada, and around the world also use LCSH to provide subject access to their collections. LCSH includes free-floating subdivisions (topical and form), Genre/Form headings, Children's (AC) headings, and validation strings for which authority records have been created. The content includes name headings (personal and corporate), such as William Shakespeare, Jesus Christ, and Harvard University, and geographic headings that are added as needed to establish subdivisions, provide a pattern for subdivision practice, or provide reference structure for other terms. *

http://purl.org/np/RAPbPkvyFnB0zf4Y80_RShjNfCZ9VBLQKvlu9IufZjnY#lcsH

3.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration

This question has not been answered yet!

3.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Library of Congress Name Authority File (LCNAF)

The Library of Congress Name Authority File (NAF) file provides authoritative data for names of persons, organizations, events, places, and titles. Its purpose is the identification of these entities and, through the use of such controlled vocabulary, to provide uniform access to bibliographic resources.

<http://purl.org/np/RAAUdJ7dOf4YIjk8hpseyBdwjxsh6P4rZLVmaWmGauXII#lcnaf>

3.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration

This question has not been answered yet!

3.b.1.d.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Humanities and Social Science Electronic Thesaurus (HASSET)

*Developed by the UK Data Service, HASSET is the leading British English thesaurus for the social sciences. It consists of over 4,000 concepts and covers the core social science disciplines: politics, sociology, economics, education, law, crime, demography, health, employment, information and communication technology, history and, increasingly, environmental science. It was originally developed from the UNESCO thesaurus, becoming a separate product in 1997. *

<http://purl.org/np/RAEtVO3E0WtabDjzJIFmOgqxjl-3xkSITHI7T1QGtTC-4#hasset>

3.b.1.d.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.d.3

Implementation Consideration

This question has not been answered yet!

3.b.1.e.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT)

*The Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus is intended to provide terminology and other information about the objects, artists, concepts, and places important to various disciplines that specialize in art, architecture, and other material culture. The primary users of the thesaurus include researchers in art and art history, museums, art libraries, archives, visual resource collection catalogers, conservation specialists, archaeological projects, bibliographic projects concerned with art, and the developers and information specialists who are dealing with the needs of these users. *

<http://purl.org/np/RACDrTxN8u5QI0hNGhHDV1pEWisdUyYzS-oknJNOuLZ9c#aat>

3.b.1.e.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.e.3

Implementation Consideration

- This question has not been answered yet!*

3.b.1.f.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Homosaurus

*The Homosaurus is an international linked data vocabulary of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, and Queer (LGBTQ) terms. This vocabulary is intended to function as a companion to broad subject term vocabularies, such as the Library of Congress Subject Headings. *

<http://purl.org/np/RAkaanpx9ThwPJuHKsUSBQtvEkS4eaCX4p4hW67KIFOpk#homosaurus>

3.b.1.f.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.f.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3.b.1.g.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Logainm Placenames Database of Ireland

The Placenames Database of Ireland is a comprehensive management system for placenames data, records and research of the State. It is a public resource for Irish people at home and abroad, and for all those who appreciate the rich heritage of Irish placenames.

<http://purl.org/np/RAbZwgg19jjofRe-fNc6lRHRrUr-rfUUzCyRJYOJ1H9XA#logainm>

3.b.1.g.2

This implementation choice is:

✔ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.g.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3.b.1.h.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS 3)

The NUTS classification is a hierarchical system for dividing up the economic territory of the EU and the UK for the purpose of the collection, development and harmonisation of European regional statistics and the socio-economic analyses of the regions. NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions; NUTS 2: basic regions for the application of regional policies and NUTS 3: small regions for specific diagnoses.

<http://purl.org/np/RAOHq4u3yUtYpqdw1ZYFpBhFIZwoGsG3uTk7TZYUzWDqI#nuts3>

3.b.1.h.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.h.3

Implementation Consideration

- This question has not been answered yet!*

3.b.1.i.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Faceted Application of Subject Terminology (FAST)

FAST (Faceted Application of Subject Terminology) is derived from the Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH), one of the library domain's most widely used subject terminology schemas. The development of FAST has been a collaboration of OCLC Research and the Library of Congress.

http://purl.org/np/RAmzU0K7f1xYrDa44WwaN7X0Nmmfujrw7oN5C_XY3ZI4A#fast

3.b.1.i.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.i.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3.b.1.j.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

PeriodO Gazetteer

PeriodO is a public domain gazetteer of scholarly definitions of historical, art-historical, and archaeological periods. It eases the task of linking among datasets that define periods differently. It also helps scholars and students see where period definitions overlap or diverge.

<http://purl.org/np/RAHhtlXC4y5LJrWPwN9tLEILCL11g0ZwFD140PzcAmw-g#periodo>

3.b.1.j.2

This implementation choice is:

✔ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.j.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3.b.1.k.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

UNESCO Thesaurus

The UNESCO Thesaurus is a controlled and structured list of terms used in subject analysis and retrieval of documents and publications in the fields of education, culture, natural sciences, social and human sciences, communication and information. Continuously enriched and updated, its multidisciplinary terminology reflects the evolution of UNESCO's programmes and activities.

<http://purl.org/np/RAQvq3sCDou186q0s151LjBLnSWIQPg3qhomWiDMj9c8w#unesco-thesaurus>

3.b.1.k.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.k.3

Implementation Consideration

- This question has not been answered yet!*

4

Declaration I2 Datasets: What structured vocabulary do you use to encode your datasets

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

4.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

4.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Exchangeable Image File Format (EXIF)

Exchangeable image file format is a standard that specifies formats for images, sound, and ancillary tags used by digital cameras, scanners and other systems handling image and sound files recorded by digital cameras.

<http://purl.org/np/RA28xyUcJMFGNEbj2kCluwQgCMKWzm1XaMJybh5UzFvtk#exif>

4.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- This question has not been answered yet!

5

Declaration I3 Metadata: What semantic model do you use for your metadata records?

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

5.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

5.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

The Dublin Metadata Element Set, which is often called Dublin Core (DC), is a standardized metadata scheme for description of any kind of resource such as documents in electronic and non-electronic form, digital materials (such as video, sound, images, etc) and composite media like web pages. Dublin Core Metadata may be used for multiple purposes, from simple resource description, to combining metadata vocabularies of different metadata standards, to providing interoperability for metadata vocabularies in the Linked Data cloud and Semantic Web implementations. Please note that this version of the specification for the Dublin Core Element Set 1.1 is somewhat out of date, although it is not officially deprecated. The DCMI Metadata Terms specification is linked to this record and is the current documentation that should be used for the Dublin Core Element Set 1.1.

http://purl.org/np/RApwFvegOdPfNuKIF64wctAzaffAv3j_2kAU9y6kfBoy8#DCMI

5.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- This question has not been answered yet!*

6

Declaration I3 Datasets: What semantic model do you use for your datasets?

- a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

VI. Declarations for Reusability

Questions

1

Declaration R1.1 Metadata: Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

CC BY 4.0 | Attribution 4.0 International

Using this licence you are free to share and adapt the resource but you must give appropriate credit.

http://purl.org/np/RAQ_sGdY_Qc7I1O_zmn4nr-pMBOxKU04Ur9s998rS6Fc#CC-BY-4.0

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

1.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CC0 1.0 | CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication

You can copy, modify, distribute and perform the work, even for commercial purposes, all without asking permission.

<http://purl.org/np/RAq55jS4TCF-u0HLARDjWevzMv8k-NY7737bSJVzRAY2w#CC0-1.0>

1.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration

This license only applies to metadata published to Europeana.

2

Declaration R1.1 Datasets: Which usage license do you use for your datasets?

b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3

Declaration R1.2 Metadata: What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

4

Declaration R1.2 Datasets: What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

4.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

4.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DC | Dublin Core

The Dublin Metadata Element Set, which is often called Dublin Core (DC), is a standardized metadata scheme for description of any kind of resource such as documents in electronic and non-electronic form, digital materials (such as video, sound, images, etc) and composite media like web pages. Dublin Core Metadata may be used for multiple purposes, from simple resource description, to combining metadata vocabularies of different metadata standards, to providing interoperability for metadata vocabularies in the Linked Data cloud and Semantic Web implementations. Please note that this version of the specification for the Dublin Core Element Set 1.1 is somewhat out of date, although it is not officially deprecated. The DCMI Metadata Terms specification is linked to this record and is the current documentation that should be used for the Dublin Core Element Set 1.1.

http://purl.org/np/RApwFvegOdPfNuKIF64wctAzaffAv3j_2kAU9y6kfBoy8#DCMI

4.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

This question has not been answered yet!

5

Declaration R1.3: Your community uses this FAIR Implementation Profile to link to domain-relevant community standards.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

VII. Register a new resource as a nanopublication

Questions

No questions